

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
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MODERN MINIMALLY INVASIVE APPROACHES IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS**Umirov M.B.^{1,3}, Kurbonov N.A.^{1,2,3}, Davlatov S.S.³, Rakhmanov K.E.⁴**¹Kashkadarya Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center, Karshi, Uzbekistan²Kashkadarya Regional Health Department, Karshi, Uzbekistan³Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Bukhara, Uzbekistan⁴Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Resume. Gallstone disease remains one of the leading conditions in surgical practice. The study included the results of surgical treatment in 138 patients with acute cholecystitis. All surgical procedures and clinical and diagnostic observations were performed at the Department of General Surgery of the Kashkadarya Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center during the period from 2022 to 2025. The patients' ages ranged from 18 to 89 years, with females predominating (84.8%). The diagnosis of acute cholecystitis was established based on clinical presentation, laboratory findings, and instrumental examination data. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in 25 patients (65.8%) with mild disease (Grade I) and in 13 patients (17.3%) with moderate severity (Grade II). In all cases, intraoperative findings included an enlarged and tense gallbladder, often associated with adhesions to the greater omentum or adjacent organs. In 31.6% of cases, gallbladder puncture with evacuation of 30–50 ml of bile was required. Intraoperative signs of acute obstructive cholecystitis were identified in 47.4% of patients, while phlegmonous cholecystitis with destructive changes of the gallbladder wall was observed in 21% of cases. Standard cholecystectomy was performed in 36 patients, whereas laparoscopic cholecystectomy with choledochal drainage according to Vishnevsky was carried out in 2 patients. The results obtained demonstrate that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a reliable, safe, and cost-effective method for the surgical treatment of acute cholecystitis. We believe that with a cautious and individualized approach, the use of minimally invasive techniques provides optimal clinical outcomes and reduces the risk of postoperative complications.

Keywords: gallstone disease, acute calculous cholecystitis, laparoscopic cholecystectomy, choledochal drainage, rehabilitation.

ЎТКИР ХОЛЕЦИСТИТНИ ЖАРРОҲЛИК ЙЎЛИ БИЛАН ДАВОЛАШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ МИНИИНВАЗИВ ЁНДАШУВЛАР**Умиров М.Б.^{1,3}, Курбонов Н.А.^{1,2,3}, Давлатов С.С.³, Рахманов К.Э.⁴**¹Қашқадарё вилоят кўп тармоқли тиббиёт маркази, Қарши ш., Ўзбекистон²Қашқадарё вилояти соғлиқни сақлаш бошқармаси, Қарши ш., Ўзбекистон³Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон⁴Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Ўт-тош касаллиги жарроҳлик амалиётида етакчи ўринлардан бирини эгаллаб келмоқда. Тадқиқотга ўтқир холецистит билан касалланган 138 нафар беморда амалга оширилган жарроҳлик даволаш натижалари киритилди. Барча оператив аралашувлар ҳамда клиник-диагностик кузатувлар Қашқадарё вилояти кўп тармоқли тиббиёт марказининг умумий жарроҳлик бўлимида 2022–2025 йиллар давомида бажарилди. Беморларнинг ёши 18 ёшдан 89 ёшгача бўлиб, уларнинг аксариятини аёллар ташкил этди (84,8%). Ўтқир холецистит таъхиси клиник белгилар, лаборатор кўрсаткичлар ҳамда инструментал текширувлар натижаларига асосланиб қўйилди. Лапароскопик холецистэктомия касалликнинг енгил кечиши (Граде I) бўлган 25 нафар беморда (65,8%) ва ўртача оғир кечиши (Граде II) бўлган 13 нафар беморда (17,3%) бажарилди. Барча кузатувларда операция вақтида ўт пуфагининг катталашгани ва таранглашигани аниқланиб, кўпинча катта салқин ёки атрофдаги аъзолар билан битишималар мавжудлиги қайд этилди. 31,6% ҳолатларда ўт пуфагини пунксия қилиш орқали 30–50 мл миқдорида ўт суюқлиги эвакуация қилинди. Операция жараёнида ўтқир обтурацион холецистит белгилари 47,4% беморларда, ўт пуфагининг деструктив ўзгаришлари билан кечувчи флегмоноз холецистит эса 21% беморларда аниқланган. 36 нафар беморга стандарт холесистектомия бажарилган бўлса, 2 нафар беморда Вишневский усули бўйича холедохни дренажлаш билан лапароскопик холесистектомия амалга оширилди. Олинган натижалар лапароскопик холецистэктомия ўтқир холециститни даволашда ишончли, хавфсиз ва иқтисодий жиҳатдан самарали усул эканлигини кўрсатади. Бизнинг фикримизча, беморларни

даволаида индивидуал ва эҳтиёткор ёндашув қўлланилганда миниинвазив технологиялар энг яхши клиник натижаларга эришиш ва асоратлар хавфини камайтириш имконини беради.

Калим сўзлар: ўт-тош касаллиги, ўткир калькулёз холецистит, лапароскопик холецистэктомия, холедохни дренажлаш, реабилитация.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МИНИИНВАЗИВНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ОСТРОГО ХОЛЕЦИСТИТА

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Резюме. Желчнокаменная болезнь по-прежнему занимает одно из ведущих мест в структуре хирургической патологии. В исследование включены результаты хирургического лечения 138 пациентов с острым холециститом. Все оперативные вмешательства и клинико-диагностические наблюдения были выполнены в отделении общей хирургии Кашкадарьинского областного многопрофильного медицинского центра в период с 2022 по 2025 годы. Возраст больных варьировал от 18 до 89 лет, при этом большинство пациентов составляли женщины (84,8%). Диагноз острого холецистита устанавливался на основании клинической картины, лабораторных показателей и данных инструментальных методов исследования. Лапароскопическая холецистэктомия была выполнена у 25 пациентов (65,8%) с лёгким течением заболевания (Grade I) и у 13 больных (17,3%) со среднетяжёлым течением (Grade II). Во всех случаях во время операции отмечались увеличение и напряжение желчного пузыря, нередко с выраженным спаечным процессом с большим сальником или соседними органами. В 31,6% наблюдений потребовалась пункция желчного пузыря с эвакуацией 30–50 мл желчи. Интраоперационные признаки острого обтурационного холецистита выявлены у 47,4% пациентов, а флегмонозное воспаление с элементами деструкции стенки желчного пузыря - у 21% больных. Обычная холецистэктомия была выполнена у 36 пациентов, в то время как у 2 больных проведена лапароскопическая холецистэктомия с дренированием холедоха по Вишневскому. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что лапароскопическая холецистэктомия является эффективным, безопасным и экономически обоснованным методом лечения острого холецистита. По нашему мнению, при взвешенном и дифференцированном подходе к ведению пациентов с острым холециститом применение лапароскопической холецистэктомии позволяет достичь лучших клинических результатов.

Ключевые слова: желчнокаменная болезнь, острый калькулёзный холецистит, холецистэктомия, дренирование холедоха, реабилитация.

Relevance. Gallstone disease (GSD) continues to occupy one of the leading positions in the structure of surgical pathology of the abdominal organs. Despite significant advances in diagnostics and treatment, the management of patients with gallstone disease and its complicated forms remains one of the most pressing problems in abdominal surgery, which is due to the steady increase in morbidity and the frequency of complications.

Acute calculous cholecystitis is diagnosed in 8–13.4% of patients admitted to surgical hospitals and predominantly occurs in elderly and senile patients. At the same time, in young individuals gallstone carriage is most often asymptomatic, and only 1–4% of such patients develop clinical manifestations in the form of biliary colic attacks. In the absence of timely treatment, acute obstructive cholecystitis develops in approximately 20% of cases.

Of particular concern is the rapidly progressive course of the inflammatory process, which may be accompanied by the development of phlegmon, gangrene, and perforation of the gallbladder, significantly increasing the risk of mortality. An increase in intravesical pressure is considered the key pathogenetic factor responsible for the development of necrobiotic changes in the gallbladder wall. In elderly and senile patients, mortality from acute cholecystitis remains high, largely due to the increased incidence of destructive and obstructive forms of the disease. It has been established that destructive forms of cholecystitis occur almost nine times more frequently in elderly patients compared to younger age groups.

Under modern conditions, a reduction in postoperative mortality and complication rates in acute cholecystitis directly depends on timely diagnosis, correct interpretation of clinical and instrumental data at both

preclinical and clinical stages, as well as on the rational choice of treatment strategy, including optimal timing and extent of surgical intervention.

Currently, three main methods of gallbladder removal are used in clinical practice: laparoscopic cholecystectomy, cholecystectomy through a right subcostal “mini-access,” and conventional open cholecystectomy via a midline approach. Among these, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is considered the “gold standard” for the treatment of acute calculous cholecystitis due to its lower invasiveness, reduced rate of postoperative complications, shorter hospital stay, and faster patient rehabilitation.

In this regard, issues of early diagnosis, optimization of conservative therapy, justified selection of the method and extent of surgical intervention, determination of the timing of surgery, and staging of treatment in gallstone disease remain extremely relevant and require further study, standardization, and implementation of modern clinical protocols.

Materials and Methods. The study included the results of surgical treatment of 138 patients with acute cholecystitis. All surgical procedures and clinical and diagnostic observations were carried out at the Department of General Surgery of the Kashkadarya Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center during the period from 2022 to 2025.

The patients’ age ranged from 18 to 89 years, with a mean age of 58.7 years. Females predominated among the examined patients - 117 individuals (84.8%), while males accounted for 21 patients (15.2%).

Diagnosis of acute cholecystitis was performed in accordance with the Tokyo Guidelines, with mandatory assessment of disease severity. Surgical risk stratification was carried out using the APACHE II (Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II) scoring system. A high surgical risk was defined as an APACHE II score ≥ 7 , which served as the basis for selecting the treatment strategy and determining the extent of surgical intervention.

The preoperative diagnosis was established based on a comprehensive evaluation of clinical, laboratory, and instrumental data. Clinical criteria included pain in the right upper quadrant, a positive Murphy’s sign, and fever. Laboratory parameters included leukocytosis and elevated C-reactive protein levels. Instrumental diagnostics were based on the detection of characteristic signs of acute cholecystitis, such as gallbladder wall thickening, presence of gallstones, gallbladder enlargement, edema, and signs of abscess formation.

Ultrasound examination of the abdominal organs was the primary imaging modality and was performed in all patients. Computed tomography was carried out in 25 patients (18.1%), mainly in cases of severe or atypical disease course. MR cholangiography was performed in 12 patients (8.7%) when choledocholithiasis was suspected.

According to imaging data, acute calculous cholecystitis was diagnosed in 117 patients (84.8%), acute acalculous cholecystitis in 9 patients (6.5%), and isolated gallstone disease without signs of inflammation in 12 patients (8.7%). Histopathological examination revealed acute cholecystitis in 78 patients (56.5%), gangrenous cholecystitis in 34 patients (24.6%), and exacerbation of chronic cholecystitis in 26 patients (18.9%).

Depending on the surgical treatment method, all patients were divided into three groups.

Table 1.

Distribution of Patients by Groups and Type of Surgical Intervention

Parameter	Group 1 (Laparoscopic)	Group 2 (Mini-access)	Group 3 (Laparotomy)	Total
Number of patients	38 (27.6%)	75 (54.3%)	25 (18.1%)	138
Mean age, years	39.5	56.0	56.5	58.7
Females	32 (84.2%)	62 (82.7%)	23 (92.0%)	117
Males	6 (15.8%)	13 (17.3%)	2 (8.0%)	21
Grade I	25 (65.8%)	13 (17.3%)	—	38
Grade II	13 (34.2%)	62 (82.7%)	—	75
Grade III	—	—	25 (100%)	25

Laparoscopic - laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Results. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed in 25 patients (65.8%) with mild disease (Grade I) and in 13 patients (34.2%) with moderate severity (Grade II). In most cases, surgery was carried out within the first 24 hours after hospital admission following standard preoperative preparation, including

antibacterial therapy, infusion correction, and surgery under balanced anesthesia with mechanical ventilation. The mean duration of laparoscopic surgery was 46.5 minutes.

Intraoperatively, all patients demonstrated an enlarged and tense gallbladder, often adherent to the greater omentum or adjacent organs. Gallbladder puncture with evacuation of 30–50 ml of bile was required in 12 patients (31.6%). Signs of obstructive cholecystitis were observed in 18 patients (47.4%), while phlegmonous-destructive changes were identified in 8 patients (21%).

Mini-laparotomic cholecystectomy was predominantly performed in patients with moderate disease severity. The mean length of the surgical access was 5.5 ± 0.1 cm, and the mean operation time was 63.8 ± 2.2 minutes. Conventional laparotomy was applied in patients with severe disease (Grade III) in the presence of pronounced inflammatory infiltrate and purulent-destructive changes.

Figure 1. Distribution of surgical treatment methods (%).

Discussion. The obtained data confirm the feasibility of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in the treatment of acute calculous cholecystitis. The absence of severe intraoperative complications and a low conversion rate indicate the safety of the method when appropriate timing of surgery is observed. The mini-laparotomic approach demonstrated high effectiveness even in purulent-destructive forms of the disease, providing favorable immediate outcomes and a low complication rate.

Conclusions:

1. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a reliable, safe, and cost-effective method for the treatment of acute cholecystitis.
2. Mini-laparotomic cholecystectomy represents a full-fledged minimally invasive technique that allows effective treatment of patients with various forms of acute cholecystitis, including gangrenous and phlegmonous forms.
3. The application of a differentiated approach to the selection of surgical technique contributes to a reduction in complication rates, mortality, and duration of rehabilitation.

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